

An Analysis Between Leadership Style, Job Satisfaction, And Organizational Commitment On Readiness To Change In Bureaucracy Reform: In The State Cyber And Password Agencies Through Work Motivation As An Intervening Variables

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 02 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 03, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Readiness for Change, Work Motivation, Leadership Style, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6325911</p>	<p><i>This research study aims to see the effect between leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment on readiness for change in the context of Bureaucratic Reform in the National Cyber and Crypto Agency through work motivation as an intervening variable. The sample was used in this study was 133 respondents who were taken using simple random sampling technique. The results were using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method with the AMOS version 24 application shown that leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment can increase work motivation. Leadership style, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work motivation can increase readiness for change, respectively. The work motivation as a mediating or intervening variable has a partial mediation effect, which can increase the influence between leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, respectively, on readiness for change.</i></p>

Introduction

According to (Kasali, 2017) argued that change is one proof of life, so change should be a normal thing for humans. However, many do not realized that they do not even respond to these changes. Disruption (a theory to predict the future, where every new thing makes the old obsolete) does not only penetrate the world of industry and business, but also to the government sector. In the government sector, to deal with current disruption, the government's first step that must be taken is to participate in changing its bureaucratic side. The bureaucracy must be more efficient and existing regulations must be simplified and reviewed, so the hope is a society will be more just and prosperous.

Along with developments, in 2010 the government launched a program of bureaucratic change known as Bureaucratic Reform (RB). In essence, RB is one of the government's efforts to implement reforms and fundamental changes to the governance system, especially regarding institutional (organizational) aspects (business processes) and human resources of the apparatus to achieve good governance. The RB has been announced since 2010 through Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 81 of 2010 concerning the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform 2010-2025.

The National Cyber and Crypto Agency (BSSN) as a government agency must implement the RB in order to support government programs as mandated. The achievement of the BSSN RB index assessment in 2018 got a value of 75.02, which means that BSSN received an increase in the performance allowance from 70% to 80%. This makes the allowances that will be given to BSSN employees will be better. However, if you look at the increase from 2017 to 2018, the RB BSSN index achievement value can only increase by 1.4%. This is different from previous years which experienced a greater increase. This illustrated that there are still many things that need to be improved by BSSN in an effort to achieve the RB achievement index target value of 100% (one hundred percent).

In addition, in 2019 there was a change in the method of assessing the reform index, such as from the Independent Assessment of the Implementation of Bureaucratic Reform (PMPRB) 2.0 to PMPRB 2.5. Currently, the initial evaluation of an object of evaluation is only for government agencies to be added to the work unit, which means that each employee in the work unit can be a sample for assessment. In addition, Kemenpan RB also stated that all Ministries / Agencies and Government Agencies would welcome the change

in the reform index assessment method to PMPRB 4.0. There will be another change in the new assessment method, making BSSN have to be ready to change to face changes in methods, so BSSN can improve its RB index assessment. This is in accordance with the statement of the Head of the Subdivision of Internal Bureaucratic Reform, Bayu Kurniawan who stated that Employees need to be more prepared to face RB (Kurniawan, 2019). Therefore, every employee must have the readiness to change in order to face RB in the future BSSN.

One factors can support the readiness to change is the leadership style. The leader's ability to motivate, communicate and build a team is a strong determining factor for implementing successful change (Gilley et al., 2009). Transformational leadership style has a positive effect on readiness to change (Triwulan, 2014). In addition, according to (Ryan & Tipu, 2013), the ability of a leader has a strong and positive influence on the trend of innovation. The leadership style can impact to the process of initiating change (Talim, 2012). However, in this research study by (Susyanto, 2019) said about a leadership factor did not directly affect readiness to change. In addition, job satisfaction can also impact readiness to change. High job satisfaction has a positive effect on readiness to change (Susyanto, 2019). Moreover, some employees who have a high level of job satisfaction will have a more positive attitude towards change and can reduce employee resistance to change (Anggraini, 2016). However, in the research study (Repsi, 2020) said that any job satisfaction did not have a significant impact to individual employee readiness to change. Organizational commitment is also an external factor for individuals related to readiness to change. In this research study by (Widiarti & Baidun, 2016), it was stated that there was a significant impact to an organizational commitment on readiness to face change. In addition, research results (Madsen et al., 2005) also shown that there is a significant relationship between readiness to change and organizational commitment. In the research (Suwaryo et al., 2015) also stated that organizational commitment has a positive impact with readiness to change. However, in research (Qureshi et al., 2018) and (Nordin, 2011) assumed that it turns out about organizational normative commitment has no significant impact with readiness to change.

Based on the previous research above, a research gap was obtained or differences in the results of research findings related to the relationship between leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment to readiness to change. Therefore, in an effort to find out the factors that can influence readiness to change in the framework of RB at BSSN, it is necessary to conduct research on the influence of leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment to readiness to change in the framework of RB in BSSN. To be able to clarify these factors, this study will use work motivation as an intervening variable. As it is known that work motivation can also affect readiness to change. Work motivation of each individual can significantly influence readiness to change (Rahmi, 2018). Work motivation is an individual's internal and external encouragement to change behavior (Uno, 2014). In relation to readiness to change, employees who have high work motivation, will tend to be more willing to work better in terms of readiness to change in the organization.

TEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Readiness to Change

Readiness to change is defined as a comprehensive attitude that is simultaneously has been influenced by the content (what changes), the process (how change is implemented), the context (where the environment for change can occur), and the individual (the characteristics of the individual who is required to change) involved in an organization. The readiness to change from an individual describes the extent to which an individual or group of individuals tends to agree, accept, and adoption to a specific plan that aims to change the current state (Holt et al., 2007).

(Holt et al., 2007) stated that readiness to change is a multi-dimensional construct consisting of 4 (four) dimensions, such as:

- a. Appropriateness, which describes aspects of an individual's belief that the proposed change will be right for the organization and the organization will benefit from implementing the change
- b. Change specific efficacy, which describes aspects of individual beliefs about their ability to implement the desired changes, where the individual feels they have the skills and are able to perform tasks related to change.
- c. Management support, which describes aspects of an individual's belief or perception that leaders and management will support and commit to the planned changes.
- d. Personal Valence, which describes that aspects for individuals feel about the benefits they feel personally that will be obtained if the change is implemented.

Leadership Style

According to (Rivai & Mulyadi, 2012) said that, leadership style is a set of characteristics that a leader does to influence his subordinates with the aim of achieving organizational goals. In addition, according to (Sutarto, 2016), leadership is the ability to influence the behavior of individuals or groups of people to achieve certain goals in certain situations.

According to (Nawawi, H, 2015), the leadership function has two dimensions, including:

- a. Dimensions related to the level of ability to direct the actions or activities of the leader, which can be seen in the responses of the people they lead;
- b. Dimensions relating to the level of support or involvement on each people, who are led in carrying out the main tasks of the group or organization, which are described and manifested through the decisions and policies of the leader.

In addition, according to (Wahyudin, 2006) in (Aprianti, 2018) leadership indicators consist of functions, as follows:

- a. Instructive function (inform)
- b. Consultative Function (peddling)
- c. Participation Function (includes)
- d. Delegation function (delegate)

Job Satisfaction

According to (Hasibuan, 2013) in (Sugiono, 2018) it was stated that job satisfaction is an attitude of pleasure and love for work as evidenced by discipline and achievement and work morale. Job satisfaction is an assessment that reflects a person's pleasure and satisfaction at work (Rivai, 2013).

(Luthans 2012) defines job satisfaction as a happy or positive emotional stated that comes from a job appraisal or a person's work experience which consists of five dimensions, such as:

- a. The work itself
- b. Salary
- c. Promotion
- d. Supervision
- e. Coworkers

Organizational Commitment

(Allen & Meyer, 1993) in (Aprianti, 2018) explained that organizational commitment is a psychological condition of a person that describes the employee's relationship with his organization, and influences for the employee's decision to continue his membership in the organization. In addition, high organizational commitment will tend to support changes made by individuals (Madsen et al., 2005).

(Allen & Meyer, 1993) in (Aprianti, 2018) suggested that there are three components of organizational commitment indicators, such as:

- a. Affective commitment, occurs when employees want to be part of the organization because of an emotional bond.
- b. Continuous commitment, occurs when employees stay in an organization because they need a salary and other benefits or because the employee cannot find another job.
- c. Normative commitment, arises from the values in employees. Employees survive to become members of the organization because of the awareness that commitment to the organization.

Work Motivation

(Robbins & Judge, 2013), defines motivation as a process that explains the intensity, direction, and persistence of an individual to achieve his goals. The three main elements in the definition are intensity, direction and persistence. Intensity is related to how hard a person tries. In addition, (George & Jones, 2011) argued that work motivation is a psychological force within a person that determines the direction of behavior, level of effort, and persistence in facing obstacles in the organization. These three parts are indicators of work motivation, whereas:

- a. Behavioral direction, refers to the behavior that individuals choose while working
- b. The level of effort, refers to the level of individual effort at work
- c. The level of persistence, refers to the mental individual in dealing with problems

METHODOLOGY

Research Model Framework

The research model framework in this article and the theories used to construct indicators are described as follows:

Sample Procedure

This research uses simple random sampling method. So, the provisions of sampling using 7 (seven) times the number of indicators, where there are 19 (nineteen) indicators in this research model. The number of samples required in this study is $19 \times 7 = 133$ samples (Ghozali, 2011), which are distributed proportionally to each work unit. Respondents based on gender consisted of 63% male and 35% female. Based on the position, it consists of 14% structural, 44% functional, and 42% implementing. Meanwhile, based on tenure, 47% had worked 1-8 years, 36% had worked 8-16 years, and 17% had worked more than 16 years.

Analysis Technique

Normality and outlier tests were carried out on the data obtained to test the normality of a data, so that it could be seen whether the data was normally distributed or not. After normality and outliers test is carried out, the construct reliability & validity test is carried out to see whether each indicator used to form a variable is able to reflect that variable. Then, it was performed SEM Full Model analysis in the form of confirmatory factor analysis test, goodness of fit test, and structural model analysis. After that, a hypothesis is tested to answer the predetermined hypothesis.

RESULTS

Test Confirmatory Factor Analysis

A variable is stated to have good validity of the construct or its latent variable if it meets the following conditions (Wijanto 2008):

- a. Value CR (Critical Ratio) > 1.96 and probability (p) < 0.05
- b. Standardized loading factors ≥ 0.50 . Hair et al., 1995 stated that the standard factor load (FMS) ≥ 0.50 is very significant.

Table 1. CFA Test Results

	Estimate	*R ²	C.R.	P	Effect
GK4 <--- Leadership Style	1.000	.511			Fact

		Estimate	*R ²	C.R.	P	Effect
GK3	<--- Leadership Style	2.578	.782	4.93	***	Fact
GK2	<--- Leadership Style	2.886	.850	5.047	***	Fact
GK1	<--- Leadership Style	2.653	.842	5.026	***	Fact
KK5	<--- Work Satisfaction	1.000	.971			Fact
KK4	<--- Work Satisfaction	.635	.635	7.647	***	Fact
KK3	<--- Work Satisfaction	.714	.705	9.139	***	Fact
KK2	<--- Work Satisfaction	.622	.948	20.575	***	Fact
KK1	<--- Work Satisfaction	.606	.604	7.129	***	Fact
KO3	<--- Organization Commitment	1.000	.763			Fact
KO2	<--- Organization Commitment	.998	.736	6.417	***	Fact
KO1	<--- Organization Commitment	.816	.750	6.421	***	Fact
MK ₁	<--- Work Motivation	1.000	.765			Fact
MK ₂	<--- Work Motivation	1.029	.777	7.146	***	Fact
MK ₃	<--- Work Motivation	1.057	.751	6.709	***	Fact
KB4	<--- Prepare/Readiness for change	1.000	.689			Fact
KB3	<--- Prepare/Readiness for change	1.191	.762	6.962	***	Fact
KB2	<--- Prepare/Readiness for change	1.515	.931	8.004	***	Fact
KB1	<--- Prepare/Readiness for change	1.495	.861	7.683	***	Fact

Noted *) Standardized Loading Factors

Source: Processed Results of AMOS Version 24

Based on Table 6 above, it is known that each indicator of the research latent variables has a CR (Critical Ratio) value > 1.96 and significant with a value of $p = 0.001$ (***) sign or below probability (p) < 0.05 (Ghozali 2011). The calculation results are shown that each indicator is valid because, it has a standard loading factor value > 0.50. This means that there is no need for modification on the model and all latent variable constructs of research are acceptable (Wijanto 2008). The relationship between indicators and latent variables is presented

with the coefficient of determination (R²). In the table above, it is known that each indicator used in this study has a positive and significant effect on the latent variable with the coefficient of determination (R²) in the significance of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Full Model Feasibility Test

There is a comparison test between the sample covariance matrix and estimated covariance matrix is called by the feasibility test or the goodness of fit test. Goodness of fit is to test whether the resulting model can describe the actual condition or not. The test criteria also consist of three types, such absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices and parsimony fit indices. The following are the results of the resulting goodness of fit test:

Table 2. Goodness of Fit Test Results

No	TEST FOR TOOLS	CRITERIA	DATA RESULTS PROCESSED	RESULTS
Absolute Fit Indicators				
1	Chi-square (χ^2)	$\chi^2_{hitung} \leq \chi^2_{table}$ (sig 0.05, df 142 = 170.809)	169.918 < 170.089	Good Fit
2	Probabilities (p)	$p > 0.05$	0.55 > 0.05	Good Fit
3	CMIN/DF	$CMIN/DF \leq 2$	1.197 \leq 2	Good Fit
4	GFI	GFI = 1 \rightarrow perfect fit, 0.9 \leq GFI < 1 \rightarrow good fit 0.8 \leq GFI < 0.90 \rightarrow marginal	0.842 < 0.90	Marginal fit
5	RMSEA	RMSEA \leq 0.05 \rightarrow closed fit 0.05 < RMSEA \leq 0.08 \rightarrow good fit 0.08 < RMSEA \leq 0.10 \rightarrow marginal fit RMRSEA > 0.10 \rightarrow poor fit	0.045 \leq 0.05	Closed Fit
Incremental Fit Indices				
6	AGFI	AGFI = 1 \rightarrow perfect fit 0.9 \leq AGFI < 1 \rightarrow good fit 0.8 \leq AGFI < 0.90 \rightarrow marginal fit AGFI < 0.80 \rightarrow poor fit	0.789 < 0.80	Poor fit
7	TLI	TLI \geq 0.9 \rightarrow good fit 0.8 \leq TLI < 0.90 \rightarrow marginal fit	0.968 \geq 0.9	Good Fit
8	NFI	NFI \geq 0.9 \rightarrow good fit 0.8 \leq NFI < 0.90 \rightarrow marginal fit	0.860 < 0.90	Marginal Fit
Parsimony Fit Indices				
9	PNFI	0.6 < PNFI < 0.9	0.714	Good Fit
10	PGFI	0 < PGFI < 1	0.629	Good Fit

Source: Processed Results of AMOS Version 24

In (Haryono 2016), according to Ghazali (2012), Wijanto (2008), Waluyo (2011), Wijaya (2009), and Widarjono (2010), it is stated that overall goodness of fit can be assessed based on at least 5 (five) criteria . In empirical research, researchers are not required to meet all the goodness of fit criteria, but it depends on the judgment or decision of each researcher. In addition, in (Haryono 2016), Latan's opinion (2012) cites the opinion of Hair et al., (2010) stated that the use of four to five goodness on fit criteria is considered sufficient to assess the feasibility of a model, provided that each criterion of goodness of fit, such absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices and parsimony fit indices that are represented or have met the good fit criteria. Table 7 above shown that there are seven out of ten criteria is meet good fit. In addition, each criterion of goodness of fit consisting on absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices and parsimony fit indices has also been represented, there are good fit criteria. Therefore, it can be concluded that the overall results of the model in this study have met the fit model criteria.

Structural Model Analysis

The next step after confirmatory factor analysis test and the full model feasibility test are fulfilled is the structural model analysis stage by looking at the influence and relationship between exogenous and endogenous latent variables. The following is a picture of the full research model in the study and the table of data

Table 3. Standardized Regression Weights

		Estimate
Work Motivation	<--- Leadership Style	.360
Work Motivation	<--- Work Satisfaction	.228
Work Motivation	<--- Organization Commitment	.345
Prepare to change	<--- Work Satisfaction	.210
Prepare to change	<--- Work Motivation	.276
Prepare to change	<--- Leadership Style	.273
Prepare to change	<--- Organization Commitment	.262

Source: Processed with AMOS Version 24

Table 4. Squared Multiple Correlations

	Estimate
Work Motivation	.503
Prepare to change	.604

Source: Processed with AMOS Version 24

Based on the table above, a coefficient of determination (R-square) of the work motivation variable is 0.503, means that the work motivation variable can be explained by the leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment variables by 50.3%, while the remaining 49.7% is another variable not examined in this study. In addition, in the variable readiness to change the value of the coefficient of determination (R-square) is 0.604, which means that readiness to change is influenced by leadership style, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work motivation variables of 60.4% while the remaining 39.6% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

The structural equation of Work Motivation (MK) explains the causal relationship between changes in MK when there is a change in the independent variables, namely Leadership Style (GK), Job Satisfaction (KK), and Organizational Commitment (KO) or $MK = f(GK, KK, KO)$. While the structural equation Readiness to Change (KB) explains the causal relationship between changes in Employee Performance (KP), with Leadership Style (GK), Job Satisfaction (KK), Organizational Commitment (KO), and Work Motivation (MK) or $KB = f(GK, KK, KO, MK)$. So, the structural equation of exogenous variables to endogenous variables is as follows:

The structural equation of the total effect between GK, KK, and KO through MK as an intervening to family planning:

Table 5. Standardized Total Effect

	Organization Commitment	Work Satisfaction	Leadership Style	Work Motivation
Work Motivation	.345	.228	.360	.000

	Organization Commitment	Work Satisfaction	Leadership Style	Work Motivation
Prepare to change	.358	.273	.372	.276

Source: Processed with AMOS Version 24

$$KB = 0.372GK + 0.273KK + 0.358KO + 0.276MK$$

$$R^2 = 0.604$$

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is conducted to determine whether or not the independent variable influences between dependent variable and research variable. The relationship between constructs in the hypothesis is indicated by a value of output regression weight. Testing the direct effect hypothesis was carried out based on the Critical Ratio (CR) value and the Probability (p) value of a causal relationship from the processing results with the provisions of acceptance such hypothesis if the CR value is < 1.96 and p value > 0.05 (Ghozali, 2011). The values used are based on the following Table 12:

Table 6. Regression Weights

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Lable
Work Motivation	<-- -	Leadership Style	.624	.264	2.368	.018	par_17
Work Motivation	<-- -	Work Satisfaction	.151	.065	2.325	.020	par_18
Work Motivation	<-- -	Organization Commitment	.264	.112	2.354	.019	par_19
Prepare to change	<-- -	Work Satisfaction	.157	.065	2.415	.016	par_16
Prepare to change	<-- -	Work Motivation	.311	.158	1.967	.049	par_22
Prepare to change	<-- -	Leadership Style	.533	.262	2.033	.042	par_23
Prepare to change	<-- -	Organization Commitment	.226	.115	1.968	.049	par_24

Source: Processed with AMOS Version 24

It to determine the value of the direct effect between exogenous variables on endogenous variables is based on Table 13 below.

Table 7. Standardized Regression Weights

			Estimate
Work Motivation	<-- -	Leadership Style	.360
Work Motivation	<-- -	Work Satisfaction	.228
Work Motivation	<-- -	Organization Commitment	.345

			Estimate
Prepare to change	<-- -	Work Satisfaction	.210
Prepare to change	<-- -	Work Motivation	.276
Prepare to change	<-- -	Leadership Style	.273
Prepare to change	<-- -	Organization Commitment	.262

Source: Processed with AMOS Version 24

In addition, to determine the value of the indirect effect between exogenous variables on endogenous variables is based on the table below.

Table 8. Standardized Indirect Effect

	Organization Commitment	Work Satisfaction	Leadership Style	Work Motivation
Work Motivation	.000	.000	.000	.000
Prepare to change	.095	.063	.099	.000

	Organization Commitment	Work Satisfaction	Leadership Style	Work Motivation
Work Motivation	.345	.228	.360	.000
Prepare to change	.358	.273	.372	.276

Source: Processed with AMOS Version 24

As a testing the indirect effect hypothesis in terms of mediation or intervening effect test is carried out using the Variance Accepted For (VAF) method (Preacher and Hayes 2008) because the results of the path coefficient has a direct influence of the research model are known. The calculation of the effect between mediation or intervening through indirect influence using the calculation of the VAF is calculated using the following formula below:

- VAF > 80%, then the mediation variable is full mediation
- $20\% \leq \text{VAF} \leq 80\%$, then the mediation variable is partial mediation
- VAF < 20%, then the mediating variable is not a mediator

Based on the foregoing, interpretation of hypothesis test is summarized with test results table, as follows:

Table 9. Recapitulation of Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	PATH	PATH COEFFICIENT	CR > 1.96	P VALUE sig < 0.05	RESULTS
				VAF Value	

H ₁	Direct	GK→MK	0.360	2.363	0.018	Significant	Accepted
H ₂	Direct	KK→MK	0.228	2.325	0.020	Significant	Accepted
H ₃	Direct	KO→MK	0.345	2.354	0.019	Significant	Accepted
H ₄	Direct	GK→KB	0.273	2.033	0.042	Significant	Accepted
H ₅	Direct	KK→KB	0.210	2.415	0.016	Significant	Accepted
H ₆	Direct	KO→KB	0.262	1.968	0.049	Significant	Accepted
Hypothesis	PATH	PATH COEFFICIENT	CR > 1.96	P VALUE sig < 0.05		RESULTS	
				VAF Value			
H ₇	Indirect GK→MK→KB	GK→MK	0.360	2.363	0.018	Significant	Accepted
		MK→KB	0.276	1.967	0.049	Significant	
		GK→KB	0.273	2.033	0.042	Significant	
		GK→KB (intervening MK)	0.372	VAF Value = 26.6% (0.099 dari 0.372)		Partial mediation	
H ₈	Indirect KK→MK→KB	KK→MK	0.228	2.325	0.020	Significant	Accepted
		MK→KB	0.276	1.967	0.049	Signifikan	
		KK→KB	0.210	2.415	0.016	Signifikan	
		KK→KB (intervening MK)	0.273	VAF = 23% (0.063 from 0.273)		Partial mediation	
H ₉	Indirect KO→MK→KB	KO→MK	0.345	2.354	0.019	Significant	Accepted
		MK→KB	0.276	1.967	0.049	Significant	
		KO→KB	0.262	1.968	0.049	Signifikan	

						t	
		KO→KB (intervening MK)	0.358	VAF Value= 26.5% (0.095 dari 0.358)		Partial mediation	
H ₁₀	Direct	MK→KB	0.276	1.967	0.049	Significan t	Accepted

CONCLUSION

This study proves that the variables of leadership style, job satisfaction and organizational commitment can increase work motivation. The variables of leadership style, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work motivation can increase readiness to change, respectively. The work motivation variable as a mediating or intervening variable has a partial mediation effect which is able to increase the influence of leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, respectively, on readiness to change.

Leadership style is the variable that has the strongest influence on work motivation which then increases readiness to change, so that BSSN can increase the readiness to change employees by starting to improve leadership abilities with good leadership styles. Starting from the ability to give instructions (instructive function), the ability to consult subordinates (consultative function), the ability to participate in work (the participation function), to the ability to share tasks (delegate function).

Eventually, this can be done by providing training to leaders in order to improve leadership skills and assign leadership tasks such as providing coaching and counseling, providing objective assessments to subordinates, and so on with the aim of making the leader figure more trained and closer to his subordinates. Thus, it increasing work motivation and readiness to change from subordinates. In choosing BSSN leaders, they must also pay attention to competencies ranging from managerial, socio-cultural, to technical candidates who will be appointed to leadership positions so that the elected leaders are leaders who are competent and able to increase motivation, readiness to change and organizational performance. It is hoped that the existing leadership in BSSN can trigger increased readiness to change in order to achieve a better index of bureaucratic reform.

In addition, BSSN can also increase job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work motivation of BSSN employees. This can be done by meeting the needs of employees starting from providing jobs that are in accordance with their abilities and can provide challenges for employees, increasing employee capabilities, transparency, understanding, salaries, benefits, increasing support facilities, and other activities that aim to foster a sense love, increase employee satisfaction, and work motivation towards the BSSN organization. The hope is that by increasing this, it can increase readiness to change employees in order to achieve a better index of bureaucratic reform.

These findings raise new implications, which means that the work motivation variable that plays a partially mediating role is not the only intervening variable, but there are still other variables that can mediate the relationship between leadership style, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, respectively, to readiness to change. which were not analyzed in this study. Therefore, it is possible for further research to find other mediating or intervening variables that can increase the readiness to change variable even better.

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